

Career Development Plan-Year 1

(Draft)

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BRIEF OVERVIEW OF RESEARCH PROJECT AND MAJOR ACCOMPLISHMENTS EXPECTED (half page should be sufficient):

Climate Change is the major global challenge of this century, with significant ramifications on human life. Unfortunately, it is unlikely that agreed climate targets can be met without removing CO₂ from the atmosphere. Negative Emissions Technologies are needed. The specific objective of the current project is thus to develop a carbon negative technology which can produce power and heat at low cost and which can be implemented rapidly. Chemical Looping Combustion (CLC) of biofuels (such as: pyrolysis oils, biogas, solid biomass) can be such a process and is the basis of the project. Biomass absorbs CO₂ during growth and releases it when burnt; but if CO₂ is captured after combustion this will result in a net flow of carbon out of the atmosphere, i.e. Carbon Negative Technology, or Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS). CLC is a form of unmixed combustion which uses an oxygen carrier to transfer oxygen from air to fuel and permits to have a pure flow of CO₂, which can be easily captured at a low cost. The aim of the project is to develop a multifuel CLC combustor which can be coupled with a Gas Turbine (GT). The combustor will work with new multi-metals oxides, to be used as oxygen carriers. These will be prepared and characterized with respect to their structural and microscopic properties, and finally tested in a pilot plant, based on circulating fluidized bed reactor. Particular attention will be focused on biofuels injection, combustor design and reaction kinetics modeling. An approach that will analyze first the oxygen carrier particle behavior, then the reactor performance will be adopted. Finally, the results will be used to scale up the process and couple the combustor with a gas turbine, designing an innovative power plant together with a leading industrial partner, which will exploit the results. It is expected that the project will generate important results, in order to implement an ambitious concept, needed for earth and society.

LONG-TERM CAREER OBJECTIVES (over 5 years):

1. Goals

The long terms goals in my Career Development Plan (CDP) are the following:

- Gain a permanent position as senior scientist or full/associate professor in a relevant University or Research Institute;
- Build a research group of at least 5 members;

- Link the activity of the Research group to relevant multinationals in the field of energy (eg. Baker Hughes) closing fruitful contracts to develop carbon negative technologies
- Win a Horizon Europe project as coordinator or member of the consortium and demonstrate the capability to attract research funds through the following funding programs (eg. PRIMA and LIFE programs);
- Become a top 2% scientist in the world, as per Stanford science-wide author databases of standardized citation indicators¹;
- Gain an ERC project which can support the realization of the first PCLC-GT-NEG plant.
- Develop a consultancy agency on decarbonization technologies, combustors modelling and innovative combustion technologies development;

2. What further research activity or other training is needed to attain these goals?

- As far as the research activity is concerned, it is needed to demonstrate at pilot scale the Pressurized Chemical Looping Combustion technology, first at the scale of a microturbine (100 kW) and then at the scale of commercial gas turbines (12—16 MW);
- Further training on grant writing, project management, financial aspects in project management, innovation, entrepreneurship, finance and leadership is needed;
- Also training in advanced teaching methods (like Problem Based Learning and Project Based Learning is needed);
- Communication and dissemination tasks have to be improved with targeted training and participation to events and conferences
- Mentoring activities have to be improved through exercise and training on pedagogic aspects and methods.
- Increase of contacts with incubators and financing institutions to increase fund raising activities continuing on the activities developed as a Climate Pact Ambassador

Long term professional development will be based on previous applications assessments, see table 1.

Table 1: Requirements to find a permanent position in Academia

Type of application	Requirements
Assessment Lapperanta University	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scientific Research (High Impact factor, Books, Citations number; Keynote presentations and awards; Editing work, PhD supervision); - Academic teaching (High quality teaching; up-to-date portfolio; development of teaching products; Supervision of thesis); - Academic Leadership (managing research groups; Leadership experience); - Acquisition of funding - Activity in the Scientific community (International Scientific Societies; other duties) - Societal impact (visibility in societal dialogue; corporate funding; professional experience; Innovation, patents and spin-offs; Activity in

¹ <https://elsevier.digitalcommonsdata.com/datasets/btchxktzyw/3>

	University stakeholders groups).
Assessment Tampere university	“He would likely benefit from developing assertive negotiation skills, in order to get his full talent in use.” From the judgement we infer that Leadership is the skill which has to be boosted.
Assessment Aalborg	- Teaching qualifications (Experience, teaching level, methods, curricular development, developing material for teaching, evaluation, training in pedagogy etc), - Research qualifications (publications indexes, significant results; quality, novelty, impact; trend in publication; project applications, patents; collaboration with industry; research manager experience; service to authorities)
Requirements to present a successful ERC Advanced grant	Editorial responsibilities; Funding IDs; Patents; Invited Presentations; Prizes; Contribution to early career of excellent researchers

In Table 1 the following evaluation reports are presented:

1. The assessment as full or associate professor at the University of Lappeenranta on the topic: Thermal engineering;
2. The results of the Assessment report for the job of full or associate professor of Bio and Circular Economy Tenure Track.
3. The assessment at Aalborg university as: associate professor in Design within Science Technology and Innovation (STI); Professor in Engineering Design and Mechanical Engineering; Associate Professor in Thermochemical Biofuel Technology.
4. The requirements taken from the examples of curricula needed to prepare an ERC proposal Advanced, which can be accessed in the CSIC website about ERC².

From table 1 it can be inferred that further training aiming at the improvement of Leadership, skills, Societal Impact and Activity in the Scientific Community.

Together with this, training on CV and cover letter writing, together with LinkedIn website implementation and training for interview delivery will be performed, using the support of some platforms, such as:

- VMOCK tool based on AI (<https://www.vmock.com/dashboard/resume>);
- TopResume (<https://topresume.portal.careers/>).

A career coach has been identified and contacted to help as well (Oliver Boberg, email: oboberg@gmx.net).

SHORT-TERM OBJECTIVES (1-2 years):

1. **Research results**
 - o Anticipated publications

The following publication program is proposed for year 2021:

² <https://intranet.csic.es/erc1>

1. Pietro Bartocci, Alberto Abad, Arturo Cabello Flores, Margarita de las Obras Loscertales Navarro, Ilmenite: a promising oxygen carrier for the scale-up of chemical looping;
 2. Alberto Abad, Francisco García-Labiano, Teresa Mendiara, Pilar Gayán, María T. Izquierdo, L.F. de Diego, EXPLORING DESIGN OPTIONS FOR PRESSURIZED CHEMICAL LOOPING COMBUSTION OF NATURAL GAS;
 3. Decarbonization (deadline 12 December, contact: Rachel Storry)
 4. Processes (special issue "Modelling, Simulation and Control in Combustion Processes of Renewable Fuels".) (Deadline end of December)
 5. Energies (modeling of oxygen carriers at molecular level, deadline 24th May 2022³)
- Anticipated conference, workshop attendance, courses, and /or seminar presentations:

For 2021-2022 I plan to provide the following contributions to conferences:

1. Poster at the Multiphase conference of Dresden⁴: Bartocci, A. Abad, M. de las Obras Loscertales Navarro, A. Cabello Flores, A. Taiana, T. Joronen, J. Konttinen, F. Fantozzi, "Batch fluidized bed model in MFIX software for simulation of chemical looping combustion, 18th Multiphase Conference & Short Course, 8-12/11/2021 Dresden;
2. ICAE 2021, November 29th December 2nd⁵
3. ASME 2022, 13-17th June 2022⁶
4. Iconbm 2022, 5-8 June 2022⁷

2. Research Skills and techniques:

Training will be performed in the specific new areas indicated in table 2. New technical expertise will be gained on the following fields: Fluidised beds main governing laws; CFD applied to fluidised beds using MFIX software; Multiphase modelling applied to fluidised beds, molecular dynamics, density functional theory, chemical processes modelling through Aspen Plus and Aspen Hysis.

³ https://www.mdpi.com/journal/energies/special_issues/chemical_looping_technology_fuel_conversion

⁴ https://eventclass.org/contxt_mpf2021/online-program

⁵ https://applied-energy.org/icae2021/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Template_ICAE2021.docx

⁶ <https://event.asme.org/Turbo-Expo>

⁷ <https://www.aidic.it/iconbm2022/>

Table 2: Training courses

Topic	Course
Fluidised Beds, see ANNEX1	Fluidized beds for conversion of solid fuels
LAMMPS ⁸⁹ , see ANNEX2	Seventh LAMMPS Workshop and Symposium
DFT	Density Functional Theory
Aspen, see ANNEX3	UDEMY
MFIX ¹⁰ , see ANNEX4	NETL 2021 Workshop on Multiphase Flow Science
Multiphase modelling ¹¹ , see ANNEX5	18 th Multiphase Flow Conference & Short Course

3. Research management:

These are the applications which can be used to gain more impact at international level:

- Application for ERC Synergy or Advanced.
- Application for Bayreuth Humboldt Centre applications;
- Applications at the Italian Ministry of Research and Universities at the Fund for Italian Science (<https://www.gea.mur.gov.it/Bandi/Fis>);
- Other visiting contracts as researcher/professor.
- Apply to the ENI AWARD
- Other possible fellowships¹².

4. Communication skills:

Training on communication skills will be performed through public dissemination events (like the Researchers Night or Science is Wonderful program; delivering webinars, delivering presentations at conferences and lessons in courses at university level). Besides this we have to consider that languages are very important to access working possibilities in different European countries so the improvement of language skills is important. With this respect language proficiency in **Spanish, German, French and English** will be required to improve my career also focusing attention on Scandinavian languages like Finnish, Danish, Swedish and Norwegian.

Besides this communication skills can be enhanced participating to events both online and in person and to dissemination and education networks such as that realised in the framework of the EU Climate Pact Ambassadors initiative.

5. Other professional training (course work, teaching activity):

Training on business and project management skills will be mainly performed at the iMBA program of the University of Illinois Urbana Champaign (online).

⁸ <https://www.lammps.org/workshops/Aug21/tutorial/>

⁹ <https://www.lammps.org/workshops/Aug21/>

¹⁰ <https://mfix.netl.doe.gov/workshop/2021-multiphase-flow-science-workshop-virtual/>

¹¹ <https://www.hzdr.de/db/Cms?pOid=47253&pNid=1296>

¹² <https://academicpositions.com/career-advice/major-postdoc-fellowships>

Other training on teaching and communication will be performed at the following events:

- Science is Wonderful
- European Researchers Night
- University of Perugia (also promoting an agreement between ICB-CSIC and UNIPG)
- HUST (also promoting collaboration between ICB-CSIC and HUST)

6. Anticipated networking opportunities

The networking strategy will be based on the following networks:

- Networking opportunities in the Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA), more than 20,000 alumni;
- Networking opportunities as Climate Ambassador
- Networking opportunities as Gies College of Business Alumni member (more than 70,000 alumni).
- FUEL editorial board;
- ENERGY NEXUS Editorial board
- ICARE Institute (China EU Institute on Clean and Renewable Energy) network of professors.

Detailed links to be used in job seeking activities are proposed in table 2, where Universities and Research Institutions of High interest and job seeking agents are reported.

Platform	Link
EURAXESS	https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/
Indeed	https://es.indeed.com/?r=us
Academic Positions	https://academicpositions.com/
Researchgate	https://www.researchgate.net/
Sintef website	https://www.sintef.no/en/sintef-group/sintef-is-looking-for-the-next-generation-of-probl/vacant-positions/
JobNorge websiste	https://www.jobbnorge.no/search
Handshake platform	https://joinhandshake.com/
Times Higher Education	https://www.timeshighereducation.com/
HigherEdJobs	https://www.higheredjobs.com/
Academic Careers	https://academiccareers.com/

Particularly important in networking will be the possibility to consider and ask for help to Italian professors abroad, like:

- Prof. Fausto Gallucci at TU Eindhoven, Europe;
- Prof. Franco Berruti at Western University, Ontario, Canada.

7. Other activities (community, etc) with professional relevance:

Other activities on which I want to focus in the mid term are:

- Improve editorial work in both journals: FUEL and ENERGY NEXUS;
- Establish contacts with relevant conferences in the Energy sector
- Prepare one book on the correct use of biomass to produce energy and bioproducts

Date & Signature of fellow:

18/11/2021

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Date & Signature of supervisor

18/11/2021

